

RAF Formulator

DISCIPLINARY PARADIGM/
RESEARCH TYPES//
RESEARCH PROCESS///
INNOVATION EXPLORER////

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RAF

RESEARCH IN
ARCHITECTURE
FORMULATOR

RAF Research in Architecture Formulation Tool © 2019 Dr Daniela A. Ottmann

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ARCHITECTURE + RESEARCH?

Architecture is a form of knowledge that can and should be developed through research, and that good research can be identified by applying the triple test of originality, significance and rigor. (Till, 2017)

Architecture research includes research projects in which trained Architects use non-disciplinary theories and methods of traditional research disciplines - for example of cultural, especially historical, but also the social and engineering. So specific architectural or building-technological questions can be pursued. This interdisciplinary founded architectural research does not originate from the design, but from traditional Architecture departments of established research disciplines. Design Research resembles a different area in research concentrating on a the 'intuitive' design/device-ing process in the tradition of artistic research.

MYTHS

Perceptions of
Architecture Research
according to Till, 2017

#1 Architecture= Architecture

A self-perpetuating paradigm

This first myth treats architecture as an autonomous discipline, beyond the reaches or control of outside influences, including those of normative research methodologies. This leads to the separation of architecture from other disciplines and their criteria for rigor. Self-referential arguments, be they theories of type, aesthetics or technique, are allowed to evolve beyond the remit or influence of accepted standards, and research into these arguments is conducted on architecture's own terms.

#2 Architecture = Architecture

Not a relevant discipline

In order to establish itself as a credible and 'strong' epistemology, architecture must turn to other disciplines for authority. Architecture is stretched along a line from the arts to the sciences and then sliced into discrete chunks, each of which is subjected to the methods and values of another intellectual area.

#3 Building a building is research

> Architectural knowledge ultimately resides in the built object

>> Every building is by definition unique and thus original

>>> The production of buildings can thus be defined as the production of original knowledge >>> This is a definition of research

FIELDS

Disciplinary paradigm of architecture

Vitruvius suggested two sets of measures of "good architecture"
 1/ ordinatio (ideological directing) - dispositio (dispositional arrangement) - eurytmia (grace of structuring) - symetria (appropriate relationships between whole and parts and among parts) - decor (composure and style consistence) - distributio (economic consideration)
 2/ Three principles of architecture:
 'firmitas – utilitas – venustas'

21st Century Architecture needs to combine both sustainable development and vitruvian tradition.

The intra-traditional scheme combining both sustainable development and vitruvian tradition. The overview in centre of figure on the right is given by Peltan, 2012. This figure depict the multi-disciplinary paradigm that architecture research gravitates surraround by disciplines like:

- arts
- anthropology
- archaeology
- ecology
- structural/mechanical/electrical/hydro/climate engineering
- economy
- history
- philosophy
- environment psychology
- law
- sociology
- industrial design
- digital technology
- material sciences
- governance
- urban planning
- urban design
- politics

Research types

DESIGN RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

Architectural design
research methodologies:
from exploration to
empirical according to
Horvath, 2007

Framing methodologies of design research from:
(a) ontological (what the framing methodologies actually are and why they exist),
(b) epistemological (what the sources, structures, and contents of knowledge are),
(c) methodological (what processes the framing methodologies imply, and what methods they involve),
and (d) praxiological (to which problems the framing methodologies have been applied, and how they are working in the practice aspects).

Methodologies typical for architectural design activities:

Design process driven research

- Individual process based research (constructive/ explorative)
- Thematic process based research (constructive/ explorative)

Design(erly) workshop driven research

- Design workshop based research (constructive/ explorative)
- Designerly workshop based research (explorative > empirical)

Design artefact/result driven research

- Individual result based research (constructive/ explorative)
- Comparative result based research (constructive/ explorative)

Design(erly) enquiry driven research

- Design data comparison based research (constructive/ explorative)
- Designerly interpretation based research (explorative > empirical)

Concrete Methods of place based design research are/

- participatory observation,
- action research,
- case study,
- protocol analysis,
- expert interviews,
- grounded theory construction, and
- assessment forums.

Exploratory

Research in design context:
(i) supports analytical disciplinary research aiming at insights, understanding and predictions, (ii) relies mainly on the knowledge of background disciplines, (iii) uses practically all research methods of these disciplines, (iv) lends itself to mono-disciplinary approaches, and (v) concentrates on building and proving theories, which add to the disciplinary knowledge of design.

Constructive

Design inclusive research
(i) supports constructive disciplinary and operative design research by involving various manifestations of design in research as research means, (ii) integrates knowledge of multiple source domains, (iii) lends itself to multi-disciplinary insights, explanations, and predictions, and (iv) generates knowledge, know how, and tools for problem solving too.

Empirical

Practice-based design research
(i) extracts knowledge from concrete practical design processes, environments, and artefacts, (ii) supports the improvement of the design problem solving intelligence reflexively, and offers generally valid principles, rules, and standards. However, the epistemological and methodological adequacy of design processes to explore genuine and general knowledge is heavily questioned. The philosophical consideration of the problem has led to the debate on the creative endeavour as a form of research. A different, but not less significant issue is that design-based research does not fit easily within the assessment parameters/judgment criteria of science funding agencies.

**SCIENTIFIC
RESEARCH +
DESIGN RESEARCH**

An overview

Knowledge is associated with formal, natural, human, social, and engineering sciences, but design research synthesizes and contextualizes even the otherwise disjoint bodies of knowledge of applied sciences for the design practice.

Architecture design research synthesises and contextualises natural, human, social and engineering sciences.

In this role, technology facilitates human, culture, environment sensitive, as well as business oriented development of products. Assuming the existence and the feasibility of enabling technologies, we can talk about a socially-inspired deployment of techno-scientific knowledge, instead of a technology-driven utilization of scientific knowledge. (Horvath, 2007)

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH PHASES

Six-stage scheme of scientific research (Figure right). This pattern of activities may occur recurrently in complex research projects. The style of research is analytical, rather than constructive. The goal is to explore, describe, understand, and explain design related phenomena, which occur naturally related to, or are partly or entirely created by design.

INNOVATION STRATEGIES + ARCHITECTURE STAGES

How did we as humans evolve over millennia from making tools (to optimise labour), utilising fire (the transfer of natural phenomena), developing language (merge bodily prerequisites with neuronal connections), inventing exchange and trade (the transfer of goods) and cultivating agriculture (to optimise food supply) to inventing industrial machines that replace human labour?

The following three innovation strategies are underlying the human capacity to innovate:

Optimise - Transfer - Fuse
(Ottmann, 2015)

Those can be questioned against the stages of architecture:

- Architectural processes
- Architectural products
- Architectural performance

CONCLUSION

This tool is developed primarily for the early stages of higher degree research in the field of architecture. It is designed to server the Phd Candidate as well as the Supervisor as a communication platform as well as a research area, process, type and hypothesis formulation tool. It comprises of a physical tetrahedron where all four sides are hierarchically equal.

The player of the RAF Research-in-Architecture-Formulator Tetrahedron can start at any side.

FIELDS/ provides a taxonomy of the various disciplinary fields in architecture.

FORMS/ tackles the research types possible that according to the field might reveal further investigations into the relevant methodology of the aimed research.

PHASES/ allows an overview of the research phases and how they are intertwined with potential thinking/investigation methods.

Lastly FINDER/ reveals aspects of innovation strategies that can be correlated with the different stages of architecture (process, product and performance).

It can also be used in a particular research process ascension, e.g. define research *field followed by research *form, research*phases and finally ask the *innovation explorer to find per architecture stage relevant innovation strategies to consider for a relevant research Hypothesis.

- Happy RAFing -

REFERENCES

FURTHER READING

Flach, A.& Kurath, M. (2016) Architektur als Forschungsdisziplin - Ausbildung zwischen Akademisierung und Praxisorientierung. Archithese, Nr. 2, 2016, S. 72-79.

Fraser, P. M. (2013). Design Research in Architecture: An Overview. Surrey, England: Ashgate Publishing.

Gordon, D. (2011) Research Methods - v2.0. Retrieved from <https://www.slideshare.net/DamianGordon1/research-methods-v20>

Horváth, I. (2007). COMPARISON OF THREE METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES OF DESIGN RESEARCH. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ENGINEERING DESIGN, PARIS, FRANCE.

Ottmann, D. & Baumeister, J. (2015) Urban Ecolution. UWAP. Perth

Peltan, T. (2012). ON TRADITIONS OF ARCHITECTURE AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: TOWARDS SYNTHESIS Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320211767>

Rangarajan, N.& and Shields, P.(2013) A Playbook for Research Methods: Integrating

Conceptual Frameworks. New Forums Press.

Shields, P. M., & Rangarajan, N. (2013). A Playbook for Research Methods: Integrating Conceptual Frameworks and Project Management.

Till, J. (2017) Architectural Research: Three Myths and One Model. Accessed 3 Oct 2019. <<https://www.archdaily.com/802766/architectural-research-three-myths-and-one-model/>> ISSN 0719-8884

Trochim, W.(2007) The Research Methods Knowledge Base. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/243783609_The_Research_Methods_Knowledge_Base

A summary of different methods used in research. (2013). Retrieved from <http://www.researchinonline.com/research-methods.html>

IMPRINT

Supervision Tool developed for candidates and supervisors of higher degrees in the field of research in architecture.

This tool does not resemble a comprehensive research methodology review. It is for information Only. The author cannot resume liability for the completeness or accuracy of any contents and information provided.

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